

Solvolytic studies in cycloalkyl systems

K. Ranganayakulu^a and N. Y. S. Murthy^{b*}

^aProfessor (Retd.), Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Warangal-506 004, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Malla Reddy Engineering College, Secunderabad-500 014, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : nysrim@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 14 May 2009, accepted 15 September 2009

Abstract : The angular dependence of the C-H/C-D bond for a stabilization of the developing carbonium ion in the transition state of the solvolysis reaction of cycloalkyl halides has been investigated. This has been achieved by studying the rate of solvolysis of eight cyclic β -deuterated 1-alkyl-1-chloro cycloalkanes. Reaction rates for the solvolysis of both β -C-H and of the corresponding β -C-D compounds have been determined and the difference in the rate ratio i.e. k_H/k_D was attributed to the differential hyperconjugative effects exerted by β -hydrogens in different ring systems. By varying the ring size from C₅ to C₁₂ the dihedral angle of C-H bond in relation to the vacant "p" orbital on the trigonal carbon, (carbonium ion transition state) changes leading to changes in hyperconjugative stabilization of the intermediate carbonium ion with a consequent change in the rate of solvolysis. β -Deuterium isotope effects thus obtained for different cyclic systems were related with the actual bond angles between β -C-H bonds and the developing carbonium ions. Using the Allinger's force field calculations the best geometry for both the carbonium ions and the starting halo hydrocarbons were calculated.

Keywords : Solvolysis, cycloalkyl systems, secondary β -deuterium isotope effects.

Introduction

Nucleophilic substitution reactions at saturated carbon atoms have been shown to proceed mainly by two different mechanisms^{1,2} viz. SN¹ and SN² mechanisms. These reactions are categorized as solvolysis reactions when solvent is the attacking nucleophile. To date there are several other mechanisms by which solvolysis reactions are known to take place (SN¹, SN^{1'}, SN^{2'} and SN^v etc.). Several workers have studied the reactions to understand more clearly the effect of changes in (a) the substrate structure, (b) the attacking nucleophile, (c) leaving group and (d) the solvent. The present work deals with the study of solvolysis of cycloalkyl halides of different ring sizes. Brown *et al.* first studied³⁻⁵ the solvolysis rates of 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclopentane and 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclohexane. It has been observed that 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclopentane undergoes solvolysis about 125 times faster than 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclohexane. Brown *et al.* have explained these results on the basis of relief of steric strain in the five membered ring system and increase in the steric strain in the case of six membered ring system in going from initial state to the transition

state. Subsequently Ranganayakulu *et al.*⁶ have studied the effect of the bulk of the side chain i.e. 1-alkyl group on the rate of solvolysis of some 1-alkyl-1-chloro cycloalkanes. We have undertaken the study of the solvolytic studies of cycloalkyl halides containing up to twelve carbons to understand more clearly the effect of the ring size on the rates of solvolysis. We have calculated the strain energies of the halo hydrocarbons and the intermediate carbonium ions and tried to correlate the difference in the strain energies with the differences in the rates of solvolysis. The data on the rate of solvolysis of 1-methyl-1-chloro cycloalkanes in 80% EtOH and H₂O at 25 °C is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Correlation of strain energy with the rates of solvolysis of 1-methyl-1-chloro cycloalkanes in 80% EtOH-H₂O at 25 °C

Sl. no.	Compd.	Strain energy ^a for most stable conformation hydrocarbon (kcal/mol)	Compd.	Strain Energy for most stable conformation of carbonium ion (kcal/mol)	Strain energy difference (kcal/mol) hydrocarbon-carbonium ion	First order rate constant <i>k</i> (s ⁻¹)
1.	Methyl cyclopentane (6)	7.78	Methyl cyclopentyl carbonium ion	6.27	1.51	3.84 × 10 ⁻⁴
2.	Methyl cyclohexane (7)	1.05	Methyl cyclohexyl carbonium ion	2.58	-1.53	3.80 × 10 ⁻⁶
3.	Methyl cycloheptane (8)	7.93	Methyl cycloheptyl carbonium ion	6.74	1.19	3.69 × 10 ⁻⁴
4.	Methyl cyclooctane (9)	12.39	Methyl cyclooctyl carbonium ion	8.08	4.31	8.86 × 10 ⁻⁴
5.	Methyl cyclononane (10)	14.97	Methyl cyclononyl carbonium ion	13.44	1.53	1.69 × 10 ⁻⁴
6.	Methyl cyclodecane (11)	13.68	Methyl cyclodecyl carbonium ion	14.12	-1.56	5.80 × 10 ⁻⁵

^aFor the calculation of strain energies of halo hydrocarbons we have taken hydrocarbons as model compounds since it is known in the literature that α-C-H and C-Cl bond have the same values for strain energy calculations.

The data in Table 1 clearly indicate that there is some correlation between strain energy difference of the initial state (hydrocarbon) and the transition state with the rate of solvolysis as far as the magnitude and the direction of strain energies are concerned; it is not completely linear in all the systems. For example both 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclopentane and 1-chloro-1-methyl cycloheptane undergo solvolysis at comparable rates but strain energy difference in these systems are found to be 1.51 and 1.19 kcal/mol respectively. Similarly the strain energy difference in the case of 1-chloro-1-methyl cyclononane system was found to be 1.53 kcal/mol but it undergoes solvolysis at a very slower rate compared to the corresponding five and six membered rings. These findings reveal that the difference in the solvolysis rates of the cyclic systems is not only due to the hydrocarbon-carbonium ion strain energies but also probably due to the differential hyperconjugative stabilization of the C-H bonds (on the β-carbon) on the developing carbonium ion in different ring systems. We, therefore, have undertaken a detailed study to verify whether there is indeed any difference in the stability of the intermediate carbonium ions generated in different ring systems. In this connection, we have

prepared the deuterated analogues of 1-chloro-1-methyl cycloalkanes (both -CD₃ and β-d₄ compounds) and compared the rates of solvolysis of the deuterated compounds with the corresponding proton analogues.

Results and discussion

The results of solvolysis of different cycloalkyl chlorides are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

The results in the Table 2 clearly indicate that k_H/k_D values are constant for all the ring systems suggesting that hyperconjugative stabilization due to β-H participation of the -CH₃ group is not the factor responsible for differences in the solvolysis rates of different ring systems. The data also suggest that the 1-alkyl group stabilizes the intermediate carbonium ion to the same extent in all the ring systems. However, the results in Table 3 clearly indicate that there is difference in k_H/k_D values for different ring systems. Secondary deuterium isotope effect is highest for five membered ring system and lowest for cyclododecane system. In order to study these differences further, we have calculated the overlap of the ring (β-C-H) C-H bond with the p-orbital at the trigonal carbon of the carbonium ion in each of the cyclic system

Note

Table 2. Rate constants for $-CH_3$ and CD_3 compounds (12 to 16) for 1-chloro-1-methyl cycloalkanes in 80% EtOH-H₂O at 25 °C

Sl. no.	Compd.	Rate constant k_H (s ⁻¹)	Rate constant k_D (s ⁻¹)	k_H/k_D
1.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclopentane	3.84×10^{-4}	3.04×10^{-4}	1.25
2.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclohexane	2.30×10^{-4} (at 60°)	1.90×10^{-4}	1.21
3.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cycloheptane	3.42×10^{-4}	2.80×10^{-4}	1.22
4.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclooctane	8.86×10^{-4}	7.40×10^{-4}	1.20
5.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclonone	1.60×10^{-4}	1.25×10^{-4}	1.28

Table 3. Rate constants for β -H₄ and β -D₄ compounds (17 to 24) for 1-chloro-1-methyl cycloalkanes in 80% EtOH-H₂O at 25 °C

Sl. no.	Compd.	(Hydrogen compound) Rate k_H (s ⁻¹)	(Deuterated compound) Rate k_D (s ⁻¹)	k_H/k_D
1.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclopentane	3.84×10^{-4}	1.98×10^{-4}	2.19
2.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclohexane	3.80×10^{-6}	2.44×10^{-6}	1.65
3.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cycloheptane	3.69×10^{-4}	2.13×10^{-4}	1.75
4.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclooctane	8.86×10^{-4}	5.79×10^{-4}	1.87
5.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclononane	1.60×10^{-4}	1.12×10^{-4}	1.59
6.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclodecane	5.80×10^{-5}	4.01×10^{-5}	1.44
7.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cycloundecane	4.02×10^{-5}	2.82×10^{-5}	1.42
8.	1-Chloro-1-methyl cyclododecane	5.12×10^{-5}	4.03×10^{-5}	1.39

from the best geometries of each molecule obtained using Allinger's force field calculations. The data are presented in Table 4.

The overlap of the C-H bond is maximum when the dihedral angle between the p-orbital on the trigonal carbon and the neighbouring C-H bond is 0° and minimum when the dihedral angle is 90°. Cos θ value gives the extent of overlap of C-H bond with p-orbital on trigonal carbon in each case. In the five membered ring system, it is now clear that the faster rate of solvolysis is due to two factors. One is due to better stabilization of intermediate carbonium ion by favourable disposition of β -C-H (ring) bonds and secondly due to the relief of steric strain⁵ in the formation of intermediate carbonium ion. In the six membered ring system the β -deuterium isotope effects suggest that the transition state may have a twist boat conformation and that the slower rate of solvolysis here is due to an extra activation energy required for the conver-

sion of a neutral chair form to the twist boat or half chair conformation prior to the actual solvolysis. The seven membered ring system probably undergoes solvolysis via twist boat-chair conformation, the eight membered ring system and nine membered ring system proceed via twist crown system and ten membered ring system via boat-boat conformation. There is no difference in the k_H/k_D values in C₁₀, C₁₁ and C₁₂ ring systems. These can be treated as open chain systems since there is no possibility of fixed ring conformation in higher ring systems. As can be seen from the results obtained using the best geometry of the intermediate carbonium ion, there is a change in the dihedral angle of the β -hydrogens with adjacent p-centre in different ring systems which will bring a change in the extent of hyperconjugation with the developing carbonium ion, and hence can account for differences in the solvolysis rates. From the ESR studies and from the observation of secondary β -deuterium isotope effects in

Table 4

Sl. no.	Conformer	Strain energy (kcal/mol) carbonium ion	Dihedral angle of most stable conformer and calculated overlap for each C-H bond with the p-orbital [cos θ values] ^a				Total overlap for four C-H bonds [cos θ values]	k_H/k_D for four C-H bonds
			H ₁	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄		
1.		6.27	35° [0.82]	35° [0.82]	35° [0.82]	35° [0.82]	3.28	2.19
2.		2.58	30° [0.866]	30° [0.866]	80° [0.1732]	80° [0.1732]	2.07	1.65
3.		5.57	10° [0.98]	10° [0.98]	60° [0.50]	60° [0.50]	2.96	1.65
4.		6.74	10° [0.98]	50° [0.64]	20° [0.93]	80° [0.1732]	2.725	1.7
5.		7.22	0° [1]	70° [0.34]	30° [0.866]	80° [0.1732]	2.342	1.75
6.		8.08	30° [0.866]	90° [0]	10° [0.98]	80° [0.1732]	2.01	1.89
7.		9.95	60° [0.50]	60° [0.50]	0° [1]	70° [0.34]	2.342	1.87
8.		10.41	10° [0.98]	90° [0]	10° [0.98]	90° [0]	1.96	1.87
9.		13.44	10° [0.98]	80° [0.1732]	10° [0.98]	80° [0.1732]	2.3	1.59
10.		13.49	30° [0.866]	90° [0]	90° [0]	30° [0.866]	1.732	1.59
11.		15.21	30° [0.866]	90° [0]	30° [0.866]	90° [0]	1.732	1.59

12.		14.40	30°	90°	30°	90°	1.732	1.44
			[0.866]	[0]	[0.866]	[0]		
13.		14.41	30°	90°	30°	90°	1.732	1.44
			[0.866]	[0]	[0.866]	[0]		
14.	1-Methyl cycloundecyl cation ^b							1.42
15.	1-Methyl cyclododecyl cation ^b							1.39

^aThe values enclosed in the parenthesis refer to the $\cos \theta$ values which gives an indication of the extent of overlap of each C-H bonds with the adjacent 'p' orbital on the trigonal carbon.

^bFor carbonium ions 1-methyl cycloundecyl cation and 1-methyl cyclododecyl cation only k_H/k_D values are given owing to the difficulties involved in the strain energy calculations. The higher ring compounds are flexible and do not have any fixed ring conformations.

bridgehead systems it has been shown that the hyperconjugation is dependent on the angle θ between the p-orbital on the trigonal carbon and the neighbouring C-H bond (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Viewing along C-C bond.

In conclusion, we can suggest that the controlling factors for the differential solvolysis rates of cycloalkyl halides arise from both the strain energy effects (hydrocarbon-carbonium ion) as well as from differential hyperconjugative stabilization of the intermediate carbonium ion.

Experimental

Preparation of starting materials :

This involves (a) preparation of $-CD_3$ compounds (12-

16) and (b) preparation of β - d_4 (ring) compounds (12-16).

Preparation of $-CD_3$ compounds (12-16) :

The overall reaction sequence involved in the preparation of title compounds is depicted in Scheme 1.

All the cyclic ketones containing C_5 to C_9 ring carbon atoms are commercially available samples. The preparation of methyl (deuterated) cycloalkyl chlorides involves the conversion of the ketones to the corresponding alcohols by treating with deuterated methyl magnesium iodide and the subsequent treatment of the alcohol with dry HCl gas in anhydrous ether.

Preparation of β - d_4 1-methyl-1-chloro cycloalkanes (17-24)⁷ :

Commercially available cyclic ketones with C_5 to C_{12} ring size are subjected to deuterium exchange with heavy water in the presence of potassium carbonate to yield β - d_4 ketones. The yield β - d_4 ketones on Grignard reaction with methyl magnesium iodide in dry ether afforded the alcohol which when treated with dry HCl gas gave the yield β - d_4 1-chloro-1-methyl cycloalkanes as shown in the following reaction sequence (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1

Measurement of solvolysis rates :

For all solvolysis rate measurements the chlorides were used to avoid F-strain effects⁸. In general, the solvolysis rates of chlorides are measured in 80% ethanol-water

mixture. Two general procedures have been followed for rate determinations. The first procedure consists of titrating aliquots of the reaction mixture consisting of alkyl chloride in eighty percent ethanol-water mixture with stan-

Scheme 2

Note

standard sodium hydroxide solution at definite time intervals. The reaction is followed up to two or three half-lives. In the second method, the rate constants were determined by using an automatic capacitance bridge with a digital control unit (Type 1673 A, General Radio Co., Concord, Massachusetts, USA). The conductance data were fed to a computer and analyzed using least square analysis for obtaining the rate constants. We have also calculated the best geometry of the transition state for each of the cyclic systems using Allinger's force field calculations⁹⁻¹¹ with the help of a computer. This will aid in the calculation of the overlap of a C-H bond on the β -carbon with the developing carbonium ion. We therefore have undertaken the solvolysis studies of the deuterated and proton compounds of the cyclic systems, from five to twelve membered rings.

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